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Nature, Culture and Literature: An Eco-Critical Contestation in Rivera's *The Vortex*

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Abstract

The natural world and human culture have remained in confrontation with each other for the time immemorial. The nature culture relationship was harmonious for many centuries of human civilisations, however, since the industrialisation process brought revolution in manufacturing and consuming, the relationship started to deteriorate and such deteriorations began to be portrayed in literature too. Jose Eustasio Rivera's novel *The Vortex* dramatizes this nature culture confrontation that was energized by the boom in western rubber industries. In this essay, I am making an argument that the novelist is giving a warning to humanity: unless human culture stops its inflicting activities to the natural world, the day of apocalypse becomes inevitable and unavoidable, when mankind will do nothing expect regretting their past actions.

Keywords: nature, culture, eco-criticism, confrontation, conflict, contestation, humanity, exploitation, subjugation

Introduction

The world has been experiencing the cases of ecocide for a few centuries now. Although early human activities like hunting, foraging, agriculture and mining made impacts on the natural world, the relation between human culture and nature remained in balance until a few centuries back. However, the balance began to deteriorate from the beginning of globalisation in the early 16th century and reached the apex after the technological and industrial breakthroughs of the 18th and nineteenth

centuries (steam power, i-c engine and electricity and industrial revolution). The technological development contributed to the consumer culture and people in the developed parts of the world started a culture of consuming more than it was necessary. Ironically, technological development exacerbated the conflict between human culture and the natural world: the more the consumption the harsher impacts on the natural world. This kind of conflict between nature and culture has been depicted in nineteenth and twentieth century European and American literature, and Colombian poet and novelist Jose Eustasio Rivera's the only novel *The Vortex* is one of the best instances to depict the conflict between human culture and natural world.

The Vortex (1924) is set in Colombian llanos of Casanare and in the Amazon rain forest describing the activities of rubber collection in the first quarter of the 20th century, popularly known as the Amazon rubber boom. The events that happen in the novel correspond the events that happened in the Amazon rain forest in the first quarter of the 20th century. The protagonist and the central narrator of the novel, Arturo Cova travels deep into the rain forest where he finds thousands of rubber tappers in pathetic condition of illness, despair, disaster and death. The Amazon rain forest abounds in rubber trees, which attracted different levels of people to the region towards the end of 19th century with the longing of earning more money in short time. Bradford L Barham and Oliver T. Coomes speak of the region, "The promise of wealth created by the boom attracted the investors, traders, adventurers, travelers, and prospective rubber workers from all over the world" (1). The presence of investors and traders and the workers at one place not only creates the ground for class struggle but also invites a contestation between natural world and human culture, the culture that evolved in the Americas from European capitalism, as William Glade claims that "Capitalism was enthroned in Latin America with the arrival of Spaniards and Portuguese" (51). The Capitalistic and patriarchal mode of production gradually took institutionalised form in the new world and came to its full swing in the time of rubber boom that became pretext for the poets and the writes.

The form of the novel is in kaleidoscope style, in which the main story narrated by a Colombian poet Arturo Cova is enclosed between the prologue, a letter written by Colombian Consul from Manaus, Brazil to the minister of Foreign Affairs in Colombia and the epilogue, a telegram

written by the same Consul to the same minister. The three-chapter sandwiched text presents the Amazon jungle as the live vortex of human destiny. The novelist presents the issues of the novel in the prologue, "I believe that this book should not be published without independent confirmation of its denunciations concerning the conditions suffered by Colombian rubber tappers in the Amazonian territories of neighboring republics" (xvii). The novelist proudly claims that the events described in the novel are true to reality.

The territories of neighboring republics, as referred by the novelist above, are the territories of Peru, Venezuela, Colombia and Brazil, the vast vegetation of the Amazon rain forest, which looks like no man's land because there is no state control from any country. This place, according to Brian Gollnick, is "inhabited by a rapacious cast of international figures intent on getting rich and leaving" (47). The culture of hoarding resources and getting rich, nurtured by European consumer capitalism, circulates through the veins of every rubber collector in the rain forest. These bovine Indians leading primitive lifestyle in the Amazonian hinterland are easily enslaved by the traders and they cannot make any kind of resistance against their own enslavement. Interestingly, although the natives do not provide any resistance, the natural world does. A new scene emerges in the novel: the humans trying to appropriate the natural world and the jungle trying resist human activities. Rivera describes a contestation between the human endeavor and the natural world true to what scholars explained as "ecocriticism" in literature in Western academia much later after the publication of *The Vortex*.

In simple words, the interpretation of literature from environmental or ecological perspective is ecocriticism. Cheryll Glotfelty defines ecocriticism, "Simply put, ecocriticism is the study of relationship between literature and physical environment" (xviii). The exploitation of the natural resources in the vast Amazonian rain forest by human beings has wider significance for the eco-critics to discuss. Rivera had eco-critical consciousness long before the coinage of the word and the germination of the concept of ecocriticism. Rivera has chosen a character to speak as the plaintiff of the natural world so as to give geo-centric message in the novel. Rivera's this choice resembles with Hochman, who explains that the animals, plants and elements cannot lodge complaints in the court themselves and human beings must speak as their plaintiffs. (190). This character Clemente Silva makes in-depth discussion why and

how the natural world resists human attacks and tries the reverse the situation. The novel, in a sense, is a document that manifests eco-critical contestation between natural world and human culture by dramatising struggle between human being and natural forces, plants, animals and elements (PAEs).

The Exploitation of the Natural World in the Americas and the Resistance

The Europeans began plundering the natural and human resources of the pristine land of the Americas as soon as they began their so-called pilgrimage in the new world. They decimated the population of the indigenous Indians within one hundred years of their occupation of the new world. The mass demographic collapse of the indigenous population is recorded by Keen and Haynes as “with an estimated loss of between 90 to 95 percent of the native population between 1492 and 1575” (57). In spite of the demographic collapse of the indigenous population the thick vegetation of the Amazon rain forest remained intact until the rubber boom of the late nineteenth century. It was in 1924 that Jose Eustasio Rivera, a Colombian national came up with his novel *The Vortex* and made the world internalize the exploitation of the Amazon rain forest in the name of tapping latex.

Rivera aphoristically sums up the environmental encroachment made in the continent in the middle of the novel within one sentence: “Who can save man from his own remorse?” (105). This sentence translates Rivera’s eco-critical consciousness. By “remorse” Rivera signals towards Western occupation and exploitation of the pristine land for 400 years or more. To explain the exploitation of the natural world and to represent this conflict between man and nature, he creates a myth of Mapiripana, the priestess and guardian of ponds and springs. Mapiripana generates water which flows through ten thousand tributaries of Orinoco and Amazon Rivers. The novelist explains, “The Indians fear her and she tolerates their activities only when they don’t disturb the peace of the forest’ (104). The quotation indicates how the Indians had coexisted in harmony with the natural world. The harmony began to deteriorate when “an evil missionary came to these latitudes, a man wearing an ecclesiastical habit who abused palm wine and Indian girls” (104). Since the arrival of the missionary, Mapiripana was always in conflict with him. The missionary’s each effort to destroy Mapiripana was foiled and eventually the missionary was imprisoned by the goddess for

many years. Because of the union of the missionary and Mapiripana an owl and a vampire bat were born, and in turn, these children began to suck their father's blood. The analogy resembles Frankenstein's monster, trying to kill its own creator. The implied meaning is clear that the Europeans' anthropocentric (the best Eurocentric) perception towards natural and human world in the Americas is brought into confrontation and this practice can ultimately devour the creators/architects themselves.

The Europeans entered the new world with two objectives: civilizing and Christianising the barbarians and they tried to rationalise their colonial activities, the exploitation of man and nature with these two objectives in their mind. They built up a clear cut binary of self and other, the European white men as the self and the Indians, blacks, women and the entire PAEs of the Americas as the other. This self-other dichotomy explained by Laurence Coupe is shown in the following diagram.

culture: nature
 male: female
 master: slave
 human: non-human
 civilised: primitive
 subject: object
 self: other (*Green Studies Reader* 119-120)

The whole novel *The Vortex* can be put in the above format of binary oppositions. The human culture is dominant over nature, or humans are dominant over non-human; the slave are dominated by the masters and the women are subordinate to men. The civilised world view (Eurocentric world view) has crushed the primitive (Indian) world view and above all humanity is in subject position or self and the natural world, the PAEs are in the object position or the other. The Europeans (the Spaniards and Portuguese in the South American continent) began to exploit the natives and plunder the entire PAEs keeping themselves in the centre. The animals were killed and their valuable organs were sent to Europe and the easy mines were exhausted in the early days of colonisation. Rivera's novel *The Vortex* provides an early twentieth-century appropriation of the Amazon rain forest for economic gain accompanying human degradation and degeneration. This essay will explore the ecological and social issues that are appropriated from anthropo/Eurocentric perspectives and how the natural world creates

obstacles and tries to prevent those activities. In short, it's capitalistic socio-economic culture of the European concept that comes in direct collision with Amazonian nature and the latter tries to resist the cultural appropriation of the natural world.

The myth of Mapiripana symbolically sets the issue in discussion and the novelist chooses a character, Clemente Silva, to express the geocentric message in the novel. Silva speaks to Arturo Cova, how man comes in conflict with the nature in the rain forest, "The tappers bleed the trees of their rubber sap, and the leeches bleed the tappers. Then the bites get infected, and they never heal. The jungle has its ways of fighting back against the intruders" (117). Nature cannot speak human language but it speaks through its forces and in the Amazon, a man has to fight many battles to survive, the battle with the mosquitos, ants and many other small and big wild animals, robbers, diseases like beriberi and above all the unwelcoming tributaries of the Amazon. Despite so many obstacles, men move to jungle driven by their greed of rubber and make confrontation with natural forces. These traders are the product of European capitalist culture of earning more money and enjoying luxurious life. The novelist ridicules this culture through the same character Clemente Silva: "The smell of rubber drives men on, beyond the normal limit of endurance. The tappers dream of becoming rich... with money in every pocket, sleeping with white women whenever they want and staying drunk for months" (117). On the contrary, the nature in the Amazon does not become welcoming to everyone and most of the tappers lose their life while hunting for money. Silva again adds, "Most end up there in the forest, burning with fever, mad as hatters, hugging the tapped trees and licking the latex sap to calm their thirst, until they fall dead and millions of ants swarm over them and pick their bones clean" (117). The contestation between culture and nature indicates that nature is not passive other, which can be appropriated by man's culture, but instead, it always tries to take its share with the intruders.

The novelist builds up certain characters to represent abuse and exploitation of human as well as natural resources. Rubber tycoons like Funes, Caynes, Barrera and Zoraida Ayram are the notorious embodiment of capitalist world of rubber business in the novel. These characters are the real people involved in the rubber business in 1920s. Eduardo Neel-Silva refers to James, an English translator of the novel, who wrote, "Funes and El Cayeno, undisguised in this story by any

pseudonym, were figures known and hated throughout the rubber world” (326). Zoraida Aryam, a Turk, was doing business in Brazil. The novelist speaks of her, “She operates a commercial house in Brazil, at Manaus. And she’s cruising all the rivers around here buying rubber and selling imported junk at astronomical prices” (119). The trick of the rubber businessmen in the early 20th century was to lend money to the workers, make them buy imported goods at high prices and put them in arrears lifelong. The novel describes the same situation through Clemente Silva:

According to law in these parts, they sign up for two years minimum, and in that time they aren’t allowed to change owners. Plus, the workers are usually in debt, and they can’t quit while they owe the company money. They are in debt because the company advances them food, tools and supplies, at exorbitant prices. Then it buys their buckets of sap at ridiculously low ones.... They can’t ever work off their debts, and when a man dies his son sometimes inherits the debt and has to slave in his father’s place. (121)

The capitalists, thus, appropriate the workers’ labor and make them collect rubber as much as possible. The workers collect much latex hoping that their debt would be paid off but the debt always remains unpaid and they work as slave their whole life. The novelist’s portrayal of the workers in debt is true to Amazonian history of rubber collection. Referring to a report in New York Times, Robert Washerstorm mentions that an English businessman Joseph Woodroffe “bought the debts 58 Indian men and 14 women and set out to collect *caucho* along the upper Tgre River” (41). This statistics shows that Rivera depended more on reality than imagination.

The novelist depicts the natural world being exploited for the resources, men being exploited for their labor and women being exploited for their body. Though Zoraida Ayram was a successful woman in rubber business, even she used her body to get success. The narrator comments on her care of body, “she worked hard to beautify her countenance, bedeck her body, and refine her overall pitch. Her glamour was essentially commercial in motivation” (175). The Indian women are portrayed in worse position than their men. Pointing to a group of girls, Clemente Silva talks to Cova, “These are our masters’ concubines. Their parents traded them for merchandise or provisions, or maybe the overseers took them just to impose their authority. They were made

concubines as soon as they reached puberty and they generally become mother while they are still children" (179). The novelist wants to convey a message that Indian women are treated merely as sexual objects.

The overseers, who work for the investors and traders, also exploit the workers by manipulating their account books. Clemente Silva speaks of such cases, "And of course, the most systematic abuse is not in the jungle, it's in the account books.... Boys who inherit enormous debts from fathers, who the company murdered, from their mothers, who the company used as prostitutes – debts that will never be paid" (137-38). Such is the plight of the workers in the rubber forest. These people either die in the company or they are sold by the company to others by receiving the amounts of their debts. The rubber companies prepare a strong workforce to collect latex. The industrialists make the people collect rubber without any kind of resistance. These capitalists have subdued the human force but the natural forces try to make attempts of resistance.

The Amazon jungle is sometimes referred to as "the green hell", from where most people do not return. The region is a fearful place with, as the novelist describes, "limitless green dungeon, surrounded by immense rivers on all sides" (148). Amazon River has its tributaries in all four countries depicted in the novel and these rivers take the lives of thousands of people every year. This is such a place, where even the mosquitoes come to one's face like a cloud. The battle with the mosquitoes is summarized by Clemente Silva, "This is a death struggle. I torture the tree and the tree tortures me until one of us succumbs" (148). After mosquitoes, Silva describes the army of tambochas, "The approach of the tambochas meant that all workers must drop their tools, leave their huts, lay down fire lines and seek refuge. Vomited from hell or who knows, the poisonous, carnivorous ants called tambochas migrate in numberless armies through the jungle" (159). The enslaved workers are in the precarious position. Their owners want latex from them and the natural forces try to stop them from collecting latex but it's humans who usually triumph over the natural forces, but, for the novelist this situation cannot go unchecked forever.

The novelist makes his spokesperson speak in favor of the natural world and through him, the novelist tries to give a message to the reader. Silva speaks of the natural world:

Man is puny, insignificant, and vulnerable in the vastness of the jungle. It would instantly triumph if all natural forces cooperated to wipe us out. But perhaps they can't. Perhaps, it isn't time for that final, cataclysmic struggle, not yet time to invoke cosmic forces and die in a blaze of glory. But the time will come here is rebellion worthy of Satan's leadership. (148-49)

Silva speaks like an eco-critical philosopher and speaks of man's vulnerability and in-significance compared to the vast natural world. The novelist has become prophetic and he means to say that time will come and the natural world will make a great leap to devour its intruders. In response to the millions of blows, the natural world will strike one blow and that will bring cataclysm in a nature-culture relationship.

The novelist concludes the novel with a partial triumph of the natural world and with a warning to humanity. He has given message that man has harbored the cause of his destruction within himself, his greed and avarice. It's the greed of man that entices him to fight with his fellow human being. Cayenne, who had five thousand slaves in the Amazon, is shot dead while he was descending downstream with a load of rubber in his canoe. Cayenne spent years in the Amazon jungle and exploited human and natural resources to the extremes but for nothing. A greedy man is shot dead by the other greedy one. The novelist passes his comments on Cayenne's death through Arturo Cova: "Good radiance to a foreign invader who came to enslave my compatriots, cut down our trees, slaughter our Indians, and steal our rubber" (213). By showing Cayenne's jungle activities and his unexpected death, the novelist gives a critique of capitalism.

Arturo Cova, the writer of the jungle stories, whom the novelist called "a player, skilled in the manly arts of deceitful seduction" (ix), finally succumbs in the sea of Amazon jungle. Cova and a few of his people including his newly born son and sick mistress Alicia are lost in the vast sea of Amazon jungle. Cova leaves his book in a jungle shelter with a letter written to Clemente Silva with a message that runs: "*Take good care of this book and put it in the Consul's hands.* The story that it tells is our story, the rubber tappers' desolate saga of abuse and suffering." (217). The novelist ends the main story of the novel with the end of the letter, in which the very last sentence reads, "God help us" (218). It's in the epilogue that the novelist brings denouement of the story with two sentences in italics, "*Clemente Silva searched unsuccessfully for five months*

finding no trace whatsoever. The jungle devoured them." It's the novelist ironic view of human destiny and vulnerability: Arturo Cova, whom the novelist called "a player in the jungle", is ultimately devoured by the jungle.

Conclusion

The novel, thus, deals with the subjugation of the poor by the rich, subjugation of women by men and subjugation of nature by culture, representing the ideas of Marxist criticism, feminist criticism and eco-critical criticism but the last one amalgamates the first two ideas. This trend of subjugation, in fact, started in Greco Roman civilisations, Christianity nurtured it and European colonialism gave institutionalised form, especially in the American continents. The myth of Mapiripana and the missionary is the explanation of European subjugation of nature in the colonial and postcolonial Americas. The orientation of western civilisation, according to Murphy is "anthropocentric" and "androcentric" (193). The anthropocentric attitude puts human being in the centre and takes plants, animals and elements as the other to be consumed by human being. The novel is a denunciation of anthropocentrism, androcentrism and class division, and above all, it's denunciation of man's atrocity towards the natural world. The novel gives a prophetic message that if humanity does not change its way of doing politics if it does not decenter from anthropocentrism, the apocalypse of humanity becomes inevitable and unavoidable. The day will come when, like Rivera's aphorism, "Who can save man from his own remorse?" the humanity, like Clemente Silva, will only have remorse.

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